

Supplementary Material

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Appendix A Notation

A list of the most commonly used notations is available in Table 1.

Appendix B Proof of Theorem 3 and Corollary 1

Given an attacker strategy $\pi_{i,t}^{(A)}$, a best response strategy $\tilde{\pi}_{i,t}^{(C)}$ is an optimal strategy in a POMDP \mathcal{M} (Thm. 2). Hence, it suffices to show that there exists an optimal strategy in \mathcal{M} that satisfies (6). Towards this end, we state and prove the following four lemmas.

Lemma 2. *The expectation in (5) is well-defined for each strategy pair π_i .*

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Notation(s)	Description
\mathcal{N}_t, N_t, f	Set of nodes, number of nodes, tolerance threshold (Prop. 1)
$T^{(R)}$	Average time-to-recovery when an intrusion occurs
$F^{(R)}, T^{(A)}$	Frequency of recovery, average service availability (4)
$T^{(f)}, k$	Time to system failure (Fig. 7), # parallel recoveries (Prop. 1)
$R(t), R_i(t)$	Reliability function for the system and for a node (Fig. 7)
J_i, J	Objectives of node controller i (4) and the system controller (7)
$\pi_{i,t}^{(C)}, \pi_{i,t}^{(A)}$	Control and attack strategy for node i (5)
$\tilde{\pi}_{i,t}^{(C)}, \tilde{\pi}_{i,t}^{(A)}$	Best response control and attack strategy for node i (5)
$\pi_{i,t}^{(C),*}, \alpha_i^*$	Equilibrium recovery strategy and best response threshold for node i (5)
$\boldsymbol{\pi}_{i,t}^*, \pi_{i,t}^{(A),*}$	Equilibrium strategy profile of Game 1 for node i , attacker equilibrium strategy
$\mathbf{i}_{i,t}^{(C)}, \mathbf{i}_{i,t}^{(A)}$	Information feedback for the controller and the attacker at time t in Game 1 (2)
$\mathbf{I}_{i,t}^{(C)}, \mathbf{I}_{i,t}^{(A)}$	Random vectors with realizations $\mathbf{i}_{i,t}^{(C)}, \mathbf{i}_{i,t}^{(A)}$ (2)
$s_{i,t}, o_{i,t}$	State (1) and observation (2) of node i at time t
$b_{i,t}$	Belief state of node i at time t (3)
$S_{i,t}, O_{i,t}, B_{i,t}$	Random variables with realizations $s_{i,t}$ (1), $o_{i,t}$ (2), $b_{i,t}$ (3)
$a_{i,t}^{(C)}, c_{i,t}$	Action and cost of the node controller i at time t (5)
$A_{i,t}^{(C)}, C_{i,t}$	Random variables with realizations $a_{i,t}^{(C)}$ and $c_{i,t}$ (5)
$a_{i,t}^{(A)}, A_{i,t}^{(A)}$	Action of the attacker on node i at time t (5)
$\mathcal{S}_N, \mathcal{O}_N$	State and observation spaces of nodes
$W, R = 0, 1$	The (W)ait and (R)ecovery actions (Fig. 3.a)
$\mathbb{H}, C = 0, 1$	The (H)ealthy and (C)ompromised node states (Fig. 3.a)
\emptyset	The crashed node state (Fig. 3.a)
$f_{N,i}, z_i$	Transition (1) and observation (2) functions for node i
$c_N(s_{i,t}, a_{i,t})$	Cost function for a node (4)
$p_{A,i}$	Probability that an attack against node i is successful (1)
$p_{C,i}$	Probability that node i crashes in the healthy state (1)
Δ_R	Maximum allowed time between node recoveries (5)
S_t, s_t	State of the system controller at time t , s_t realizes S_t
$a_t^{(C)}, c_t$	Action and cost of the system controller at time t
$A_t^{(C)}, C_t$	Random variables with realizations $a_t^{(C)}, c_t$ (8)
$\mathbf{a}_t^{(A)}, \mathbf{A}_t^{(A)}$	Action of the attacker in Game 2 (8)
f_S	Transition function of Game 2
\mathcal{S}_S	State space of Game 2
s_{\max}	Maximum number of nodes in Game 2
$\pi^{(C)}, \pi^{(A)}$	Control and attack strategy in Game 2 (8)
$\tilde{\pi}^{(C)}, \tilde{\pi}^{(A)}$	Best response control and attack strategy in Game 2 (8)
$\pi^{(C),*}, \pi^{(A),*}$	Equilibrium control and attack strategies in Game 2 (8)
$\boldsymbol{\pi}, \boldsymbol{\pi}^*$	Strategy profile and equilibrium strategy profile in Game 2 (8)
ϵ_A	Lower bound on the average service availability (8)

Table 1: Notation.

Proof. Since the sample space of the random vectors $(\mathbf{I}_t^{(C)}, \mathbf{I}_t^{(A)})$ is finite (and measurable) for each t , the space of realizable histories $\mathbf{h}_t^{(C)} \times \mathbf{h}_t^{(A)} \in \mathcal{H}_t$ is countable. By the Ionescu-Tulcea extension theorem, it thus follows that there exists a well-defined probability measure \mathbb{P} over \mathcal{H}_t for $t = 1, 2, \dots$ [35]. Further, Lemma 1 implies that the expectation is finite. \square

Lemma 3. *The controller's best response POMDP \mathcal{M} defined in (5) with the BTR constraint (5b) can be converted into a sequence of unconstrained POMDPs $(\mathcal{M}_k)_{k \geq 1}$.*

Proof. Using Lemma 1 and Lemma 2 we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \arg \min_{\pi_{i,t}^{(C)}} \mathbb{E}_{\pi_{i,t}^{(C)}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \gamma^{t-2} C_{i,t} \mid b_{i,1} = 0 \right] &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \arg \min_{\pi_{i,t}^{(C)}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{\pi_{i,t}^{(C)}} \left[\right. \right. \\ &\sum_{t=1}^{\tau_1} \gamma^{t-2} C_{i,t} \mid b_{i,1} = 0 \left. \right] + \mathbb{E}_{\pi_{i,t}^{(C)}} \left[\sum_{t=\tau+1}^{\tau_2} \gamma^{t-2} C_{i,t} \mid b_{i,\tau+1} = 0 \right] + \dots \left. \right] \\ &= \arg \min_{\pi_{i,t}^{(C)}} \mathbb{E}_{\pi_{i,t}^{(C)}} \left[\gamma^{\tau_1-1} J_i(0) + \sum_{t=1}^{\tau_1} \gamma^{t-2} C_{i,t} \mid b_{i,1} = 0 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $C_{i,t}$ is a random variable representing the cost of node i at time t ; and (a) follows from linearity of \mathbb{E} . Since $J_i(0)$ is completely determined by the recovery strategy, it can be seen as a fixed recovery cost. As a consequence, the final expression in (13) defines an optimal stopping problem. \square

Lemma 4. *The expected cost-to-go function $J_{i,t}^*(b) \triangleq \mathbb{E}_{\tilde{\pi}_{i,t}^{(C)}}[J_i \mid b_{i,1} = b]$ (4) induced by a best response strategy $\tilde{\pi}_{i,t}^{(C)}$ in \mathcal{M} (Lemma 3) is piecewise linear and concave with respect to $b \in [0, 1]$ and becomes stationary when $\Delta_R \rightarrow \infty$.*

Proof. The piece-wise linear and concave property is proven by E.J. Sondik in [1, Thm. 2]. The stationarity of J_i^* is proven by V. Krishnamurthy in [2, Thm. 7.6.1]. For completeness, we briefly outline the main ideas behind the proofs here. Recall that the cost-to-go function can be written as $J_i^*(b) = \min_i [1 - b, b]^T \boldsymbol{\alpha}_i$, where $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_1, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_2, \dots$ are the alpha vectors (see Fig. 4). Since the minimum over a set of linear functions is concave, the piece-wise linear and concave property of J_i^* follows. Next, stationarity is a consequence of the definition of Game 1 and can be shown using mathematical induction based on the iterates of the value iteration algorithm [2, Thm 7.6.3]. \square

Lemma 5. *Let $\mathcal{S}_t \subseteq [0, 1]$ denote the subset of the belief space in \mathcal{M} where it is a best response to perform recovery at time t , i.e., $b_{i,t} \in \mathcal{S}_t \iff \tilde{\pi}_{i,t}^{(C)}(b_{i,t}) = R$, then \mathcal{S}_t is a convex set.*

Proof. This result was originally proven by V. Krishnamurthy in [2, Thm. 12.2.1]. For completeness, we give the proof here since it is very short.

To show that \mathcal{S}_t is convex, we need to show that $b_1, b_2 \in \mathcal{S}_t \implies \lambda b_1 + (1 - \lambda)b_2 \in \mathcal{S}_t$ for any $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. For notational convenience, let $c(\mathbf{R})$ be the recovery cost in (13). Since $J_{i,t}^*(b)$ is concave (Lemma 4), we have

$$J_{i,t}^*(\lambda b_1 + (1 - \lambda)b_2) \geq \lambda J_{i,t}^*(b_1) + (1 - \lambda)J_{i,t}^*(b_2).$$

As $b_1, b_2 \in \mathcal{S}_t$ by assumption, the best response action given b_1 or b_2 is \mathbf{R} . Thus $J_{i,t}^*(b_1) = Q_{i,t}^*(b_1, \mathbf{R})$ and $J_{i,t}^*(b_2) = Q_{i,t}^*(b_2, \mathbf{R})$, where $Q_{i,t}^*$ is the best response Q-function in \mathcal{M} (Lemma 3). Since $Q_{i,t}^*(b_{i,t}, \mathbf{R}) = c(\mathbf{R})$ (4), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} J_{i,t}^*(\lambda b_1 + (1 - \lambda)b_2) &\geq \lambda J_{i,t}^*(b_1) + (1 - \lambda)J_{i,t}^*(b_2) \\ &\geq \lambda Q_{i,t}^*(b_1, \mathbf{R}) + (1 - \lambda)Q_{i,t}^*(b_2, \mathbf{R}) \\ &= c(\mathbf{R}) \stackrel{(a)}{\geq} J_{i,t}^*(\lambda b_1 + (1 - \lambda)b_2), \end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows because $J_{i,t}^*$ is the best response cost. This shows that, if $b_1, b_2 \in \mathcal{S}_t$, then $Q_{i,t}^*(\lambda b_1 + (1 - \lambda)b_2, \mathbf{R}) = J_{i,t}^*(\lambda b_1 + (1 - \lambda)b_2)$, which means that $\lambda b_1 + (1 - \lambda)b_2 \in \mathcal{S}_t$ for any $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. Hence, \mathcal{S}_t is convex [2, Thm. 2.2.1]. \square

B.1 Proof of Theorem 3

Lemma 5 implies that $\mathcal{S}_t = [\alpha_{i,t}^*, \kappa_t]$, where $0 \leq \alpha_{i,t}^* \leq \kappa_t \leq 1$. Thus, it suffices to show that $\kappa_t = 1$. Like in the proof of Lemma 5, let $c(\mathbf{R})$ be the stopping cost in (13). It follows from Bellman's optimality equation [3, Eq. 1] that

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{i,t}^{(\mathbf{C})}(1) &\in \arg \min_{a \in \{\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{W}\}} \left[\overbrace{\gamma^{-1}c(\mathbf{R})}^{\mathbf{R}}, \overbrace{\gamma^{-1}c_{\mathbf{N}}(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{W}) + \mathbb{E}_{\pi_{i,t}^{(\mathbf{C})}}[J_{i,t+1}^*(1)]}^{\mathbf{W}} \right] \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \arg \min_{a \in \{\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{W}\}} \left[c(\mathbf{R}), \gamma^{\tau-1}c(\mathbf{R}) + \sum_{t=1}^{\tau-1} \gamma^{t-1}c_{\mathbf{N}}(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{W}) \right] \\ &\stackrel{(b)}{=} \arg \min_{a \in \{\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{W}\}} \left[c(\mathbf{R}), \gamma^{\tau-1}c(\mathbf{R}) + \frac{\eta(1 - \gamma^{\tau-2})}{1 - \gamma} \right] = \mathbf{R}, \end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows because $s_i = \mathbf{C}$ is an absorbing state until a recovery occurs; and (b) follows from (4). As a consequence, $\tilde{\pi}_{i,t}^{(\mathbf{C})}(1) = \mathbf{R} \implies \mathcal{S}_t = [\alpha_{i,t}^*, 1]$. \square

B.2 Proof of Corollary 1

Lemma 4 states that the cost-to-go function $J_i^*(b)$ becomes stationary when $\Delta_{\mathbf{R}} \rightarrow \infty$. As a consequence, it follows from Thm. 3 and Lemma 5 that there exists a stationary best response strategy. Such a strategy induces a stationary recovery set \mathcal{S} , which means that α_i^* (6) is time-independent.

When $\Delta_R < \infty$, it follows from the Bellman equation [3, Eq. 1] and (4) that it is a best response to perform recovery at time t iff

$$c(\mathbf{R}) \leq \eta b_{i,t} + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{B_{i,t+1}} \left[J_{i,t+1}^*(B_{i,t+1}) \mid b_{i,t}, a_{i,t}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right], \quad (14)$$

where $c(\mathbf{R})$ is the stopping cost in (13) and $J_{i,t}^*$ is the best response cost-to-go function defined in Lemma 4. Hence, $\alpha_{i,t}^* \leq \alpha_{i,t+1}^*$ iff the right-hand side of (14) is non-decreasing in t for all $b_{i,t}$. This is equivalent to showing that

$$W_{i,t}(b_i) \triangleq \gamma \mathbb{E}_{B'_i} \left[J_{i,t+1}^*(B'_i) \mid b_i, a_{i,t}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right] - \gamma \mathbb{E}_{B'_i} \left[J_{i,t}^*(B'_i) \mid b_i, a_{i,t-1}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right]$$

is non-negative for all t and b_i . We prove this property using mathematical induction on $t = \Delta_R - 1, \Delta_R - 2, \dots, 1$. For $t = \Delta_R - 1$ we have

$$W_{i,t}(b_i) = \gamma c(\mathbf{R}) - \min \left[\gamma c(\mathbf{R}), \mathbb{E}_{B'_i} [\gamma \eta B'_i + \gamma^2 c(\mathbf{R}) \mid b_i, a_{i,t-1}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W}] \right],$$

which is non-negative for all b_i by definition.

Assume by induction that $W_{i,k}(b_i)$ is non-negative for all b_i and $k = t-1, t-2, \dots, \Delta_R$. We will show that this assumption implies that $W_{i,t}(b_i) \geq 0$.

There are three cases to consider:

1. If the best response actions are $a_{i,t}^{(C)} = a_{i,t+1}^{(C)} = \mathbf{R}$, then

$$W_{i,t}(b_i) = \gamma c(\mathbf{R}) - \gamma c(\mathbf{R}) = 0.$$

2. If the best response actions are $a_{i,t}^{(C)} = a_{i,t+1}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} W_{i,t}(b_i) &= \mathbb{E}_{B'_i, B''_i} \left[\gamma \eta B'_i + \gamma^2 J_{i,t+2}^*(B''_i) \mid b_i, a_{i,t}^{(C)} = a_{i,t+1}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right] - \\ &\quad \mathbb{E}_{B'_i, B''_i} \left[\gamma \eta B'_i + \gamma^2 J_{i,t+1}^*(B''_i) \mid b_i, a_{i,t-1}^{(C)} = a_{i,t}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{B'_i} \left[\mathbb{E}_{B''_i} \left[\gamma^2 J_{i,t+2}^*(B''_i) \mid B'_i, a_{i,t+1}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right] - \left[\gamma^2 J_{i,t+1}^*(B''_i) \mid B'_i, a_{i,t}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right] \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{B'_i} \left[\gamma W_{i,t+1}(B'_i) \mid b_i, a_i^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right], \end{aligned}$$

which is non-negative by the induction assumption.

3. If the best response actions are $a_{i,t}^{(C)} = \mathbf{R}$ and $a_{i,t+1}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} W_{i,t}(b_i) &= \mathbb{E}_{B'_i, B''_i} \left[\gamma \eta B'_i + \gamma^2 J_{i,t+2}^*(B''_i) \mid b_i, a_{i,t}^{(C)} = a_{i,t+1}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right] - \gamma c(\mathbf{R}) \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{\geq} \mathbb{E}_{B'_i, B''_i} \left[\gamma \eta B'_i + \gamma^2 J_{i,t+2}^*(B''_i) \mid b_i, a_{i,t}^{(C)} = a_{i,t+1}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right] - \\ &\quad \mathbb{E}_{B'_i, B''_i} \left[\gamma \eta B'_i + \gamma^2 J_{i,t+1}^*(B''_i) \mid b_i, a_{i,t-1}^{(C)} = a_{i,t}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{B'_i} \left[\gamma W_{i,t+1}(B'_i) \mid b_i, a_i^{(C)} = \mathbf{W} \right], \end{aligned}$$

which is non-negative by the induction assumption, where (a) follows from the Bellman equation [3, Eq. 1].

The case where $a_{i,t}^{(C)} = \mathbf{W}$ and $a_{i,t+1}^{(C)} = \mathbf{R}$ can be discarded due to the induction hypothesis. This completes the inductive step. It follows by mathematical induction that $W_{i,t}(b_i)$ is non-negative for all b_i and t . \square

Appendix C Proof of Theorem 5

By introducing a Lagrange multiplier $\lambda \geq 0$ and defining the immediate cost to be $c_\lambda(s_t, a_t^{(C)}) = a_t^{(C)} + \lambda \mathbb{1}_{s_t < f+1}$ we can reformulate the CMDP as a discounted Lagrangian MDP through Lagrangian relaxation [4, Thm. 3.7] and the vanishing discount method [5]. The best response strategy in this MDP satisfies

$$\tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}(s_t) \in \arg \min_{a_t^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \left[c_\lambda(s_t, a_t^{(C)}) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{S_{t+1}} \left[\tilde{J}_\lambda(S_{t+1}) \mid s_t, a_t^{(C)} \right] \right], \quad (15)$$

where $\gamma \in [0, 1)$ is a discount factor and \tilde{J}_λ is the best response cost-to-go function induced by a best response strategy $\tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}$ [4, Thm. 3.6]. Let $\tilde{Q}_\lambda(s, a^{(C)})$ be the best response Q-function associated with (15).

Our approach to proving Thm. 5 follows the approach described in [82]. The main steps of the proof are as follows. We first show that there exists an optimal threshold strategy in the discounted Lagrangian MDP for any non-negative Lagrange multiplier and discount factor $\gamma \in [0, 1)$. Next, we use the vanishing discount method [5] to establish that the threshold structure also applies under the average cost optimality criterion. We then prove that the optimal cost in the CMDP corresponds to $\inf_{\pi^{(C)}} \sup_\lambda J_\lambda$, where J_λ is the cost-to-go function in the Lagrangian MDP with the average cost optimality criterion. We then show that the sup and inf can be interchanged. As a consequence, an optimal strategy for the CMDP can be obtained by first computing an optimal strategy in the Lagrangian MDP and then maximizing with respect to the Lagrange multiplier λ . Then we note that, since the CMDP only has a single constraint, an optimal strategy in the CMDP requires at most one randomization [4, Thm. 4.4]. Consequently, there exists an optimal strategy in the CMDP that is a randomized mixture of two optimal deterministic strategies in the Lagrangian MDP for different Lagrange multipliers [83, Thm. 1]. Since there exist optimal threshold strategies in the Lagrangian MDP for any non-negative Lagrange multiplier λ , the theorem statement follows. We provide detailed proof below.

Towards the proof of Thm. 5, we start by stating and proving the following lemmas.

Lemma 6. *The expectation in (8a) is well-defined for each strategy pair π .*

Proof. Since the sample space of $(S_t, A_t^{(C)}, \mathbf{A}_t^{(A)})$ is finite (and measurable) for each t , the statement follows from Lemma 2. \square

Lemma 7. *For any $\gamma \in [0, 1)$, $\lambda \geq 0$, and $s > f$, \tilde{J}_λ has non-decreasing differences, i.e., $\tilde{J}_\lambda(s+1) - \tilde{J}_\lambda(s)$ is non-decreasing in s .*

Proof. We establish the non-decreasing differences property using the value iteration algorithm [6, Eq. 6.3.2–6.3.4]. Let $\tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}$ denote the optimal cost-to-go function at iteration k of value iteration. Then, $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k} = \tilde{J}_\lambda$ [6, Thm. 6.3.1][7, Thm. 6, p. 160]. Let $\tilde{J}_{\lambda,0}(s) = 0 \forall s$. We proceed to prove the statement using mathematical induction.

BASE CASE: $\tilde{J}_{\lambda,1}(s+1) - \tilde{J}_{\lambda,1}(s) = 0$.

INDUCTIVE CASE: Assume that $\tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}(s+1) - \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}(s)$ is non-decreasing for $k = l, l-1, \dots, 2$. There are three cases to consider:

1. If $\tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}(s+1) = \tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}(s)$, then it follows from (T5.1) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}(s+1) - \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}(s) \\ &= \gamma \mathbb{E}_{S'}[\tilde{J}_{\lambda,k-1}(S'+1) \mid S = s+1] - \gamma \mathbb{E}_{S'}[\tilde{J}_{\lambda,k-1}(S'+1) \mid S = s] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{S'}[\tilde{J}_{\lambda,k-1}(S'+2) - \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k-1}(S'+1) \mid S = s], \end{aligned}$$

which is non-decreasing in s by the induction hypothesis.

2. If $\tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}(s+1) = 0$ and $\tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}(s) = 1$, then (T5.1) implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}(s+1) - \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}(s) &= \gamma \mathbb{E}_{S'}[\tilde{J}_{\lambda,k-1}(S'+1) - \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k-1}(S'+1) \mid S = s] - 1 \\ &= -1. \end{aligned}$$

3. If $\tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}(s+1) = 1$ and $\tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}(s) = 0$, then (T5.1) implies that

$$\tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}(s+1) - \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}(s) = 1 + \mathbb{E}_{S'}[\tilde{J}_{\lambda,k-1}(S'+2) - \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k-1}(S') \mid S = s],$$

which is non-decreasing in s by the induction hypothesis.

Therefore, by mathematical induction, $\tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}(s+1) - \tilde{J}_{\lambda,k}(s)$ is non-decreasing in s for all k and $s > f$, which implies that $\tilde{J}_\lambda(s+1) - \tilde{J}_\lambda(s)$ is non-decreasing in s for all $s > f$. \square

Lemma 8. For any $\gamma \in [0, 1)$, $\lambda \geq 0$, and $s > f$, $\tilde{Q}_\lambda(s, a^{(C)})$ is supermodular [2, Eq. 9.3].

Proof. \tilde{Q}_λ is supermodular if the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{Q}_\lambda(s, 1) - \tilde{Q}_\lambda(s, 0) \leq \tilde{Q}_\lambda(s+1, 1) - \tilde{Q}_\lambda(s+1, 0) \\ \iff & \mathbb{E}_{S'}[\tilde{J}_\lambda(S'+1) - \tilde{J}_\lambda(S') \mid S = s] \leq \mathbb{E}_{S'}[\tilde{J}_\lambda(S'+2) - \tilde{J}_\lambda(S'+1) \mid S = s], \end{aligned}$$

which follows from Lemma 7. \square

Lemma 9. For any $\gamma \in [0, 1)$ and $\lambda \geq 0$, there exists an optimal strategy in the Lagrangian MDP that satisfies (15) and has the following form.

$$\tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}(s) = 1 \iff s \leq \beta \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}_S, \quad (16)$$

where $\beta \geq f$ is a threshold.

Proof. We can rewrite (15) as

$$\tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}(s_t) \in \arg \min_{a_t^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \left[c_\lambda(s_t, a_t^{(C)}) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{S_{t+1}} [\tilde{J}_\lambda(S_{t+1}) \mid s_t, a_t^{(C)}] \right]$$

$$= \arg \min_{a_i^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \tilde{Q}_\lambda(s_t, a_i^{(C)}). \quad (17)$$

Since \tilde{Q}_λ is supermodular (Lemma 8) it follows from Topkis' theorem [8, Thm. 6.1] that the minimizer of (17) is (weakly) decreasing in s . As a consequence, there exists a threshold β and a best response strategy that satisfies (16). \square

Lemma 10. *For some $\lambda \geq 0$, let $(\gamma_n)_{n \geq 1}$ be any sequence of discount factors $\gamma_n \in [0, 1]$ converging to 1 with $(\pi_{\lambda, n}^{(C)})_{n \geq 1}$ being an associated sequence of discounted best response strategies satisfying (15). Then there exists a subsequence $(v_n)_{n \geq 1}$ and a stationary strategy $\pi_\lambda^{(C)}$ that is a limit point of $(\pi_{\lambda, n}^{(C)})_{n \geq 1}$.*

Proof. This statement is proven by A. Hordijk in [73] and also used by C.Derman in [72]. A more accessible version of the proof is given by L.I Sennott in [5, Lemma 1]. For completeness, we give the proof here since it is very short.

Let \mathcal{A}_i denote the finite set of actions available in state i and assume that \mathcal{A}_i has the discrete topology. By the Tychonoff theorem [74, p. 383], the product of compact spaces is compact, and hence $\prod_i \mathcal{A}_i$ is compact and metrizable. Every stationary strategy can be regarded as a point in this space. Hence, $(\pi_{\lambda, n}^{(C)})_{n \geq 1}$ is a sequence in this space, and therefore, there exists a subsequence converging to a stationary strategy $\pi_\lambda^{(C)}$. \square

Lemma 11. *Any stationary strategy $\tilde{\pi}_\lambda^{(C)}$ obtained by Lemma 10 is a best response in the MDP obtained by replacing the discounted optimality criterion in (15) with the average cost optimality criterion.*

Proof. The statement holds if Assumptions 1-3' in [5, Thm. 1] are satisfied. Assumption 1 asserts that $J_\lambda^*(s)$ is finite for every state s , Lagrange multiplier $\lambda \geq 0$, and discount factor $\gamma \in [0, 1)$. Assumptions 2-3' require that the average cost is bounded. These assumptions follow directly from the definition of Game 2 and (T4.1)–(T4.2). In the interest of space, we do not repeat the full proof here; instead, we summarize the key ideas to aid understanding. The proof primarily relies on Tychonoff's theorem [74, p. 383], which allows to establish that the average cost is the limit of a sequence in the space. The statement of the lemma is then demonstrated by applying Fatou's lemma [74, p. 257] and the dominated convergence theorem [74, p. 50]. \square

Lemma 12. *The threshold structure in (16) is inherited by any best response strategy obtained by Lemma 11.*

Proof. Follows from Lemmas 6–11 and [9, Thm. 2.2, Remark 1]. \square

Lemma 13. *Let $\tilde{J}(\gamma)$ denote the optimal cost-to-go in the best response CMDP for the controller against an attacker strategy $\pi^{(A)}$ and let J_λ be the cost-to-go in the Lagrangian MDP with $\gamma = 1$. Then*

$$\tilde{J} = \inf_{\pi^{(C)}} \sup_{\lambda \geq 0} \mathbb{E}_{S_1}[J_\lambda(S_1)] = \sup_{\lambda \geq 0} \inf_{\pi^{(C)}} \mathbb{E}_{S_1}[J_\lambda(S_1)].$$

Proof. If the constraint (8b) is not feasible, then $\sup_{\lambda \geq 0} \mathbb{E}_{S_1}[J_\lambda(S_1)] = \infty$ for any $\pi^{(C)}$ and thus $\tilde{J} = \inf_{\pi^{(C)}} \sup_{\lambda \geq 0} \mathbb{E}_{S_1}[J_\lambda(S_1)]$. If (8b) is feasible, then the supremum is obtained by choosing $\lambda = 0$. Consequently, $J_\lambda = J$ (7). Hence $\inf_{\pi^{(C)}} \sup_{\lambda \geq 0} \mathbb{E}_{S_1}[J_\lambda(S_1)] = \inf_{\pi^{(C)}} J = \tilde{J}$. That the sup and inf can be interchanged follows from standard minimax theorems, see [4, Thm. 3.6]. \square

C.1 Proof of Theorem 5

A well-known result in Lagrangian dynamic programming theory is that there exists an optimal strategy in a CMDP with a single constraint, which is a randomized mixture of two optimal deterministic strategies of the induced Lagrangian MDP (15) with different Lagrange multipliers λ_1 and λ_2 [83, Thm. 1][2, Thm. 6.6.2][4, Thm. 12.7]. Lemma 13 implies that the Lagrange multipliers can be obtained by first computing the optimal strategies in the Lagrangian MDP and then taking the supremum over the set of non-negative Lagrange multipliers. Lemma 12 implies that for each non-negative Lagrange multiplier, there exists a deterministic strategy that has the threshold structure in (10). When combined, these three properties imply the statement of Thm. 5. \square

Appendix D Proof of Corollary 2

Consider the MDP faced by the attacker when fixing the control strategy $\pi^{(C)}$. The optimality equation in this MDP reads

$$0 = \max_{\mathbf{a}^{(A)}} \left[\pi^{(C)}(s) - g + \sum_{s'} f_S(s' | s, \pi^{(C)}(s), \mathbf{a}^{(A)}) J(s') - J(s) \right],$$

where f_S is the transition function, g is the best response average cost, $\tilde{\pi}^{(A)}$ is a best response strategy [6, Eq. 8.4.2, Thm. 8.4.3][2, Thm. 6.5.2], and $J(s)$ is defined as

$$J(s) \triangleq \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \mathbb{E}_{(S_t)_{t \geq 1}, \tilde{\pi}^{(A)}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \pi^{(C)}(S_t) \mid S_1 = s \right].$$

As a consequence, any $\tilde{\pi}^{(A)}$ satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\pi}^{(A)}(s) &\in \arg \max_{\mathbf{a}^{(A)}} \left[\sum_{s'} f_S(s' | s, \pi^{(C)}(s), \mathbf{a}^{(A)}) J(s') \right] \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \arg \max_{\mathbf{a}^{(A)}} \left[\sum_{s'} f_S(s' | s, \pi^{(C)}(s), \mathbf{a}^{(A)}) s' \right] \stackrel{(b)}{=} \arg \max_{\mathbf{a}^{(A)}} \left[\sum_{s'} \mathbb{P}[s' | s, \mathbf{a}^{(A)}] s' \right], \end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows from the fact that $J(s)$ is decreasing in s (Thm. 5, Lemma 7) and (b) follows from the definition of $a_t^{(C)}$, which implies that the attacker action $\mathbf{a}^{(A)}$ that minimizes $\mathbb{E}[S]$ is independent of $\pi^{(C)}$. \square

Appendix E Hyperparameters

Hyperparameters for the experimental results and figures reported in the paper are listed in Table 2. Confidence levels for all figures are computed based on the Student-t distribution.

Figures	Values
Fig. 3.b	$p_{C,i} = 0$
Fig. 7	$p_{C,i} = 10^{-5}$
Fig. 4.a	$\eta = 2, p_{A,i} = 0.05, p_{C,i} = 0.01, \Delta_R = 100, \mathcal{O} = 100$ $z_i(\cdot 0) = \text{BetaBin}(n = 100, \alpha = 0.7, \beta = 3)$ $z_i(\cdot 1) = \text{BetaBin}(n = 100, \alpha = 1, \beta = 0.7)$ $\pi_{i,t}^{(A)}(s, b) = \mathbf{A}$
Fig. 4.b	$p_{C,i} = 0.01, \Delta_R = \infty, \mathcal{O} = 100$ $z_i(\cdot 0) = \text{BetaBin}(n = 100, \alpha = 0.7, \beta = 3)$ $z_i(\cdot 1) = \text{BetaBin}(n = 100, \alpha = 1, \beta = 0.7)$
Fig. 6	$p_{C,i} = 0.01, p_{A,i} = 0.5, \Delta_R = \infty, \mathcal{O} = 100$ $z_i(\cdot 0) = \text{BetaBin}(n = 100, \alpha = 0.7, \beta = 3)$ $z_i(\cdot 1) = \text{BetaBin}(n = 100, \alpha = 1, \beta = 0.7)$
Fig. 10	Δ_R for the periodic strategy was selected using Bayesian optimization. $p_{C,i} = 0.05, p_{A,i} = 0.3, \Delta_R = \infty, \mathcal{O} = 100$ $z_i(\cdot 0) = \text{BetaBin}(n = 100, \alpha = 0.7, \beta = 3)$ $z_i(\cdot 1) = \text{BetaBin}(n = 100, \alpha = 1, \beta = 0.7)$
Fig. 11	$p_{A,i} = 10^{-1}, p_{C,i} = 10^{-5}, \epsilon_A = 0.9$ $s_{\max} = 13, \eta = 2, f = \min[\frac{N_i-1}{2}, 2]$ f_S estimated from simulations of Game 1 z_i estimated from testbed measurements, see Fig. 16
Incremental pruning [10, Fig. 4]	
Variation, ϵ	normal, 0
SPSA [11, Fig. 1]	
$c, \epsilon, \lambda, A, a, N, \delta$	10, 0.101, 0.602, 100, 1, 50, 0.2
M number of samples for each evaluation	50
Cross-entropy method [12][13, Alg. 1]	
λ (fraction of samples to keep)	0.15, 100
K population size	100
M number of samples for each evaluation	50
Differential evolution [14, Fig. 3]	
Population size K , mutate step	10, 0.2
Recombination rate	0.7
M number of samples for each evaluation	50
Bayesian optimization [15, Alg. 1]	
Acquisition function	lower confidence bound [16, Alg. 1]
β , Kernel	2.5, Matern(2.5)
M number of samples for each evaluation	50
HSVI [17, Alg. 1]	
$\epsilon, \text{PDELTA}, \text{PLIMIT}$	0.001, 0.005, 2000
MINBFT [18, §4.2]	
USIG implementation	RSA with key lengths 1024 bits [19]
$T_{\text{exec}}, T_{\text{vc}}, \text{cp}, L$	30 seconds, 280 seconds, $10^2, 10^3$

Table 2: Hyperparameters.

Appendix F Perfect Bayesian Equilibrium of Game 1

Following the definitions in [20, Defs. 8.2-3], we define a perfect Bayesian equilibrium (PBE) as an extension of subgame perfection for fully observed games to partially observed games as follows.

Definition 1 (Perfect Bayesian equilibrium (PBE) [21, Def. 1]). *Let \mathbb{B} denote the belief operator in (3). Then (π^*, \mathbb{B}) is a PBE iff*

1. π^* is a Nash equilibrium (NE) [36, Eq. 1] in $\Gamma|_{\mathbf{h}_{i,t}^{(C)}} \forall \mathbf{h}_{i,t}^{(C)}$, where $\Gamma|_{\mathbf{h}_{i,t}^{(C)}}$ is the subgame of (5) starting from $\mathbb{B}(\mathbf{h}_t^{(C)}, \pi_{i,t}^{*,(A)})$.
2. For any $\mathbf{h}_{i,t}^{(C)}$ with $\mathbb{P}[\mathbf{h}_{i,t}^{(C)} | \pi^*, \mathbf{b}_1] > 0$, then

$$\mathbb{B}(\mathbf{h}_{i,t}^{(C)}, \pi_{i,t}^{*,(A)}) = \mathbb{B}(\mathbb{B}(\mathbf{h}_{i,t-1}^{(C)}, \pi_{i,t}^{*,(A)}), \pi_{i,t}^{*,(C)}(\mathbb{B}(\mathbf{h}_{i,t-1}^{(C)}, \pi_{i,t}^{*,(A)})), o_t, \pi_{i,t}^{*,(A)}).$$

Definition 1 places two restrictions on equilibrium strategies: (i) strategies are required to yield a NE in every subgame defined by the continuation of a controller history $\mathbf{h}_{i,t}^{(C)}$; and (ii) beliefs are required to be updated in accordance with Bayes' rule (3) whenever applicable. In other words, a PBE is a strategy pair and a belief such that at any time-step of the game, strategies are optimal given the belief, and the belief is obtained using Bayes' rule [20, Defs. 8.2-3].

Appendix G Game 1 in Extensive Form

The extensive form representation of Game 1 is shown in Fig. 12.

Appendix H Markov Perfect Equilibrium of Game 2

Definition 2 (Markov perfect equilibrium (MPE) [22, Def. 5]). *A strategy pair $\pi^* = (\pi^{(C),*}, \pi^{(A),*})$ is a Markov perfect equilibrium of Game 2 if each player follows a Markov behavior strategy and π^* is a Nash equilibrium [36, Eq. 1] regardless of the initial state.*

Computation of an MPE for a stochastic game is, in general, a PPAD-complete problem [84, Thm. 1].

Appendix I Intrusion-Tolerant System Architecture

The system architecture induced by the system model in §3 is shown in Fig. 13. We name the architecture **TOLERANCE**, which stands for Two-level recovery and replication control with feedback. A detailed architecture description can be found in [23].

Fig. 12: Game 1 in extensive form; a filled circle denotes a decision node; an unfilled circle denotes a chance node; the first label next to each node indicates the player who makes the decision; N denotes nature; the second label next to each node and the dashed lines indicate the information sets; a zig-zag branch is a short-hand for many branches; a triangle indicates a subgame; $\Gamma|_{h_{i,t}^{(C)}}$ is the subgame of (5) starting from the belief obtained using (3) based on $\mathbf{h}_t^{(C)}$.

Fig. 13: The TOLERANCE architecture; N_t nodes provide a replicated service to a client population; service responses are coordinated through an intrusion-tolerant consensus protocol; local node controllers decide when to perform recovery, and a global system controller manages the replication factor N_t .

Appendix J Intrusion-Tolerant Consensus Protocol

The TOLERANCE architecture (Fig. 13) is based on a reconfigurable consensus protocol for the partially synchronous system model with hybrid failures, a reliable network, and authenticated communication links (see Prop. 1). (In an authenticated network, nodes can verify each other’s digital signatures.) Examples of such protocols include MINBFT [18, §4.2], MINZYZZYVA [18, §4.3], REMINBFT [26, §5], and CHEAPBFT [25, §3]. Our implementation uses MINBFT. Correctness of MINBFT is proven in [18, Appendix A].

MINBFT is based on PBFT [27] with one crucial difference. While PBFT assumes Byzantine failures and tolerates $f = \frac{N-1}{3}$ failures, MINBFT assumes hybrid failures [28] and tolerates $f = \frac{N-1}{2}$ failures. The improved resilience of MINBFT is achieved by assuming access to a trusted component that provides certain functions for the protocol. In particular, MINBFT relies on a tamperproof service at each node that can assert whether a given sequence number was assigned to a message. This service allows MINBFT to prevent *equivocation* [29] and imposes a first-in-first-out (FIFO) order on requests issued by clients. (A compromised node is said to *equivocate* if it sends inconsistent information to different nodes in the system.) In TOLERANCE, the tamperproof service is provided by the virtualization layer (see Fig. 13).

We extend MINBFT [18, §4.2] to be *reconfigurable* [30], where the reconfiguration procedure is based on the method described in [31, §IV.B]. (A reconfigurable consensus protocol allows dynamic addition and removal of nodes from the system.) The different stages of the protocol are illustrated in Fig. 14, and the throughput of our implementation is shown in Fig. 15. The source code is available at [32], and the hyperparameters are listed in Table 2.

Appendix K Testbed Evaluation Setup

We implement a proof-of-concept intrusion-tolerant system on a testbed. It is a distributed system with 13 nodes connected through an Ethernet network. Nodes communicate via message passing over authenticated channels. Each node runs (i) a service replica in a Docker container; (ii) a node controller; and (iii) the SNORT IDS with ruleset v2.9.17. The service replicas run a web service and the MINBFT consensus protocol [18, §4.2]. The system controller is implemented by a crash-tolerant system that runs the RAFT protocol [76]. The source code of our implementation is available at [32].

An evaluation run evolves in time-steps of 60 seconds. It starts with N_1 nodes from Table 3, each of which runs a service replica (see Table 4). At each time-step, one or more replicas may be recovered by the node controllers, and a new node may be added by the system controller. When a replica is recovered, its container is replaced with a container selected randomly from the list in Table 4. Similarly, a node from the list in Table 3 is started when a new node is added.

Each replica has one or more vulnerabilities that can be exploited by the attacker using the steps listed in Table 6. After compromising a replica, the

Fig. 14: Time-space diagrams illustrating the message patterns of the MINBFT intrusion-tolerant consensus protocol [18, §4.2].

Fig. 15: Average throughput of our implementation of MINBFT; error bars indicate the 95% confidence interval based on 1000 samples.

<i>Server</i>	<i>Processors</i>	RAM (GB)
1, R715 2U	two 12-core AMD OPTERON	64
2, R715 2U	two 12-core AMD OPTERON	64
3, R715 2U	two 12-core AMD OPTERON	64
4, R715 2U	two 12-core AMD OPTERON	64
5, R715 2U	two 12-core AMD OPTERON	64
6, R715 2U	two 12-core AMD OPTERON	64
7, R715 2U	two 12-core AMD OPTERON	64
8, R715 2U	two 12-core AMD OPTERON	64
9, R715 2U	two 12-core AMD OPTERON	64
10, R630 2U	two 12-core INTEL XEON E5-2680	256
11, R740 2U	1 20-core INTEL XEON GOLD5218R	32
12, SUPERMICRO 7049 2 TESLA P100, 1 16-core INTEL XEON		126
13, SUPERMICRO 7049 4 RTX 8000, 1 24-core INTEL XEON		768

Table 3: Specifications of the physical nodes.

attacker randomly chooses between a) participating in the consensus protocol, b) not participating, and c) participating with randomly selected messages.

Replicas are interconnected through Gbit/s connections with 0.05% packet loss (emulated with NETEM [33]). They receive a stream of service requests, which are sent by a client over 100 Mbit/s connections with 0.1% packet loss.

To emulate IDS events for a realistic system, each replica runs a set of background services in addition to the replicated service (see Table 5). These background services are consumed by a population of background clients, who arrive with a Poisson rate $\lambda = 20$ and have exponentially distributed service times with mean $\mu = 4$ time-steps.

All parameters for the evaluation are listed in Appendix E except for z_i (2), which we estimate with the empirical distribution \hat{z}_i (see Fig. 16). We compute \hat{z}_i based on $M = 25,000$ samples [32], knowing that $\hat{z}_i \xrightarrow{\text{a.s.}} z_i$ as $M \rightarrow \infty$ (Glivenko-Cantelli theorem).

Fig. 16: Empirical distributions $\hat{z}_1(\cdot | s_1), \dots, \hat{z}_{10}(\cdot | s_{10})$ as estimates of z_1, \dots, z_{10} (2) for the containers in Table 4.

Appendix L Distributions of System Metrics

Our testbed implementation of TOLERANCE (Fig. 13) collects hundreds of metrics every time step. To measure the information that a metric provides for de-

<i>Replica ID</i>	<i>Operating system</i>	<i>Vulnerabilities</i>
1	UBUNTU 14	FTP weak password
2	UBUNTU 20	SSH weak password
3	UBUNTU 20	TELNET weak password
4	DEBIAN 10.2	CVE-2017-7494
5	UBUNTU 20	CVE-2014-6271
6	DEBIAN 10.2	CWE-89 on DVWA [34]
7	DEBIAN 10.2	CVE-2015-3306
8	DEBIAN 10.2	CVE-2016-10033
9	DEBIAN 10.2	CVE-2010-0426, SSH weak password
10	DEBIAN 10.2	CVE-2015-5602, SSH weak password

Table 4: Containers running the service replicas.

<i>Background services</i>	<i>Replica ID(s)</i>
FTP, SSH, MONGODB, HTTP, TEAMSPEAK	1
SSH, DNS, HTTP	2
SSH, TELNET, HTTP	3
SSH, SAMBA, NTP	4
SSH	5, 7, 8, 10
DVWA, IRC, SSH	6
TEAMSPEAK, HTTP, SSH	9

Table 5: Background services of the service replicas.

<i>Replica ID</i>	<i>Intrusion steps</i>
1	TCP SYN scan, FTP brute force
2	TCP SYN scan, SSH brute force
3	TCP SYN scan, TELNET brute force
4	ICMP scan, exploit of CVE-2017-7494
5	ICMP scan, exploit of CVE-2014-6271
6	ICMP scan, exploit of CWE-89 on on DVWA [34]
7	ICMP scan, exploit of CVE-2015-3306
8	ICMP scan, exploit of CVE-2016-10033
9	ICMP scan, SSH brute force, exploit of CVE-2010-0426
10	ICMP scan, SSH brute force, exploit of CVE-2015-5602

Table 6: Steps to compromise service replicas.

etecting intrusions, we calculate the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence $D_{\text{KL}}(\hat{z}_{i,O|F} \parallel \hat{z}_{i,O|A})$ between the distribution of the metric when the attacker generates false alarms $\hat{z}_{i,O|F} \triangleq \hat{z}_i(\cdot \mid A_i^{(A)} = F)$ and during an attack $\hat{z}_{i,O|A} \triangleq \hat{z}_i(\cdot \mid A_i^{(A)} = A)$:

$$D_{\text{KL}}(\hat{z}_{i,O|F} \parallel \hat{z}_{i,O|A}) = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \hat{z}_{i,O|F} \log \left(\frac{\hat{z}_{i,O|F}}{\hat{z}_{i,O|A}} \right).$$

Here $o \in \mathcal{O}$ realizes the random variable O (2), which represents the value of the metric. (\mathcal{O} is the domain of O .)

Figure 17 shows empirical distributions of the collected metrics with the largest KL divergence. We see that the IDS alerts have the largest KL divergence and thus provide the most information for detecting the type of intrusions that we consider in this paper (see Table 6).

Fig. 17: Empirical distributions of selected infrastructure metrics; the red and blue lines show the distributions when no intrusion occurs and during an intrusion, respectively.

Appendix M References for the Proof of Theorem 1

The proof of claim 1 is available in [38, Thm. 1]. The proof of claim 2 is available in [39, Thm. 1][37, Thms. 5.8,5.11][18, Thm. 2][40, Thm. 1]. The proof of claim 3 is available in [37, Thm. 5.2][41, Cor. 14] [42, Thm. 1]. Since several of these proofs span multiple pages, we omit them here for brevity. The main proof technique is to model the system using I/O automata [77].

Appendix N Confidentiality Extension of Proposition 1

There are two ways to extend the system model in §3 to provide confidentiality. One approach is to force all replicas to send messages through a firewall that filters faulty messages that may contain confidential data [43]. Another option is to use specialized cryptographic techniques, e.g., verifiable secret sharing [44].

Appendix O State-of-the-art Intrusion-Tolerant Systems

Existing intrusion-tolerant systems include PBFT [45], ZYZZYVA [46], HQ [47], HOTSTUFF [48], VM-FIT [49, 50], WORM-IT [51], PRRW [52], RECOVER [53], SCIT [54, 55], COCA [56], [57], SPIRE [58], ITCIS-PRR [59], CRUTIAL [60], UPRIGHT [61], BFT-SMART [62], SBFT [63], SITAR [64], ITUA [65, 66], MAFTIA [67], ITSI [68], and SKYNET [69]. All of them are based on intrusion-tolerant consensus protocols and support recovery, either directly or indirectly through external recovery services, like PHOENIX [70]. The game-theoretic control strategies proposed in this paper differ from the control strategies used in these systems in two main ways.

First, our game-theoretic strategies use feedback control to decide when to perform intrusion recovery. This contrasts with the control strategies in all of the referenced systems, which are based on periodic or heuristic recovery schemes. (PRRW, RECOVER, CRUTIAL, SCIT, SITAR, ITSI, and ITUA can be implemented with feedback-based recovery, but they do not specify how to implement such recovery strategies.) Second, we propose a game-theoretic strategy for adaptive replication based on feedback control. In comparison, all of the referenced systems use static replication strategies except SITAR, ITUA, and ITSI, which implement adaptive replication based on time-outs and static rules. The benefit of feedback control is that it allows the system to adapt promptly to intrusions, not having to wait for a time-out.

Appendix P Tables of Numerical Results

The numerical results used to produce Fig. 5 and Fig. 11 are listed in Tables 7–8.

Method	$\Delta_R = 5$		$\Delta_R = 15$		$\Delta_R = 25$		$\Delta_R = \infty$	
	Time (min)	J_i (4)	Time (min)	J_i (4)	Time (min)	J_i (4)	Time (min)	J_i (4)
CEM [13, Alg. 1]	1.04	0.12 ± 0.01	8.84	0.17 ± 0.06	14.48	0.19 ± 0.08	11.81	0.16 ± 0.01
DE [14, Fig. 3]	2.35	0.12 ± 0.03	8.98	0.17 ± 0.01	15.45	0.18 ± 0.02	22.68	0.16 ± 0.01
BO [15, Alg. 1]	29.18	0.12 ± 0.02	62.57	0.17 ± 0.05	90.26	0.18 ± 0.12	9.07	0.15 ± 0.06
SPSA [11, Fig. 1]	10.78	0.18 ± 0.01	88.35	0.58 ± 0.40	123.85	0.77 ± 0.48	4.20	0.20 ± 0.02
PPO [71, Alg. 1]	28.20	0.18 ± 0.01	30.01	0.19 ± 0.02	30.33	0.21 ± 0.07	28.95	0.21 ± 0.09
IP [10, Fig. 4]	11.11	0.12	237.06	0.17	743.73	0.18	> 10000	not converged

Table 7: Computing a best response for the controller in Game 1 using Alg. 1 (upper rows) and baselines (lower rows); columns represent Δ_R ; subcolumns indicate the computational time (left) and the average cost (right); numbers indicate the mean and the 95% confidence interval based on 20 random seeds.

Control strategy	$\Delta_R = 15$			$\Delta_R = 25$			$\Delta_R = \infty$		
	$T^{(A)}$	$T^{(R)}$	$F^{(R)}$	$T^{(A)}$	$T^{(R)}$	$F^{(R)}$	$T^{(A)}$	$T^{(R)}$	$F^{(R)}$
$N_1 = 3$									
BEST RESPONSE	0.99 ± 0.01	1.43 ± 0.09	0.09 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	1.43 ± 0.09	0.09 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	1.43 ± 0.09	0.09 ± 0.01
EQUILIBRIUM	0.99 ± 0.01	1.138 ± 0.08	0.06 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	1.138 ± 0.0	0.06 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	1.138 ± 0.08	0.06 ± 0.01
NO-RECOVERY	0.08 ± 0.06	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00	0.08 ± 0.06	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00	0.08 ± 0.06	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00
PERIODIC	0.97 ± 0.01	6.06 ± 1.16	0.065 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.01	8.64 ± 1.48	0.04 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.06	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00
PERIODIC-ADAPTIVE	0.95 ± 0.02	5.42 ± 0.93	0.05 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.02	6.57 ± 1.01	0.03 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.04	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00
$N_1 = 6$									
BEST RESPONSE	0.99 ± 0.01	1.47 ± 0.07	0.07 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	1.47 ± 0.07	0.07 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	1.47 ± 0.07	0.07 ± 0.01
EQUILIBRIUM	0.99 ± 0.01	1.42 ± 0.06	0.05 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	1.42 ± 0.07	0.05 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	1.42 ± 0.06	0.05 ± 0.01
NO-RECOVERY	0.16 ± 0.06	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00	0.16 ± 0.06	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00	0.16 ± 0.06	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00
PERIODIC	0.98 ± 0.01	5.96 ± 1.16	0.065 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.02	8.13 ± 1.48	0.04 ± 0.01	0.16 ± 0.03	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00
PERIODIC-ADAPTIVE	0.99 ± 0.01	5.02 ± 0.34	0.06 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.02	6.16 ± 0.54	0.03 ± 0.01	0.17 ± 0.03	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00
$N_1 = 9$									
BEST RESPONSE	1.00 ± 0.00	1.44 ± 0.05	0.07 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.00	1.44 ± 0.05	0.07 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.00	1.44 ± 0.05	0.07 ± 0.01
EQUILIBRIUM	1.00 ± 0.00	1.42 ± 0.04	0.05 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.00	1.42 ± 0.04	0.05 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.00	1.42 ± 0.04	0.05 ± 0.01
NO-RECOVERY	0.17 ± 0.04	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00	0.17 ± 0.04	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00	0.17 ± 0.04	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00
PERIODIC	0.99 ± 0.00	5.37 ± 0.34	0.06 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01	7.74 ± 0.51	0.04 ± 0.01	0.17 ± 0.04	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00
PERIODIC-ADAPTIVE	1.00 ± 0.00	4.44 ± 0.25	0.06 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	6.01 ± 0.39	0.04 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.02	$10^3 \pm 0.00$	0.00 ± 0.00

Table 8: Comparison between our game-theoretic control strategies and the baselines; columns indicate values of Δ_R ; subcolumns represent performance metrics; row groups relate to the number of initial nodes N_1 ; numbers indicate the mean and the 95% confidence interval from evaluations with 20 random seeds.

Appendix Q Preference Relations

It follows from (4) that the outcome of Game 1 is determined by the number of recoveries and the number of time-steps in the compromised state \mathbb{C} . Let α and β denote the average number of recoveries and time-steps in state \mathbb{C} , respectively. The game's outcome can then be defined as $o \triangleq \eta\tilde{\alpha} + \tilde{\beta}$. Given this definition, the preference relation \succ_i that is represented by the cost function J_i can be expressed as

$$o \succ_i \tilde{o} \iff o < \tilde{o} \quad o \approx_i \tilde{o} \iff o = \tilde{o}. \quad (18)$$

Theorem 6. *The preference relation \succeq_i (18) of Game 1 satisfies the von Neumann-Morgenstern axioms [75, p. 26].*

Proof. By definition (18), \succeq_i is reflexive, transitive and complete. Hence, it only remains to prove the continuity, monotonicity, and independence axioms. We start with the continuity axiom. Consider three outcomes $o_1 \preceq_i o_2 \preceq_i o_3$. We need to show that there exists a probability $\theta_i \in [0, 1]$ such that

$$o_2 = \theta_i o_3 + (1 - \theta_i) o_1.$$

Solving for θ_i , we get:

$$\theta_i = \frac{o_2 - o_1}{o_3 - o_1}.$$

It follows from (18) that $o_2 \geq o_3$. Hence, $\theta_i \in [0, 1]$.

Next, consider the monotonicity axiom. Suppose $o_2 \succeq_i o_1$ and let a, b be values in $[0, 1]$. We need to show that if $ao_2 + (1 - a)o_1 \leq bo_2 + (1 - b)o_1$, then $a \geq b$. We have

$$ao_2 + (1 - a)o_1 \leq bo_2 + (1 - b)o_1 \implies o_2(a - b) \leq o_1(a - b),$$

which requires that $a \geq b$.

Now consider the independence axiom. Given two outcomes $o_1 \preceq_i o_2$, any $z \in \mathbb{R}^+$, and any $p \in (0, 1)$, the axiom asserts that we must have $po_1 + (1 - p)z \geq po_2 + (1 - p)z$. This can be verified as follows.

$$po_1 + (1 - p)z \geq po_2 + (1 - p)z \implies po_1 \geq po_2 \implies o_1 \geq o_2, \quad (19)$$

which holds by definition of \succeq_i (18). \square

Corollary 3. *The preference relation \succeq of Game 2 satisfies the von Neumann-Morgenstern axioms [75, p. 26].*

Proof. It follows from (7) that the outcome of the game (given that the constraint is feasible) is determined by the number of added nodes. Let α denote the average number of added nodes. Then, the game's outcome can be defined as $o \triangleq \alpha$, and the preference relation is equivalent to (18). \square

Appendix R Proof of Theorem 4

In preparation for the proof, we first review some fundamental concepts of CMDPs that are key to our analysis [4]. A CMDP with a single constraint is defined by a five-tuple $\langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, f, c, d, V \rangle$, where \mathcal{S} is the set of states, \mathcal{A} is the set of actions, f is the transition function, c is the cost function, d is the constraint cost function, and V is the bound on the average value of d that defines the constraint. Let Π denote the space of all possible behavioral strategies in the CMDP (i.e., history-dependent behavior strategies) and let $\beta \in \Delta(\mathcal{S})$ denote the initial state distribution. Given a strategy $\pi \in \Pi$, we define the *occupation measure* $\rho \in \Delta(\mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A})$ as follows.

$$\rho_\pi(s, a) \triangleq \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{P}[S_t = s, A_t = a \mid \pi, \beta] \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, a \in \mathcal{A}. \quad (20)$$

With some abuse of notation, we also define

$$\rho_\pi(s) \triangleq \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{P}[S_t = s \mid \pi, \beta] \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, a \in \mathcal{A}. \quad (21)$$

Let $\mathcal{P}(\pi)$ be the set of occupation measures that satisfy (21) and define \mathcal{L} as the set of occupancy measures induced by Π :

$$\mathcal{L} \triangleq \bigcup_{\pi \in \Pi} \mathcal{P}(\pi).$$

Similarly, for any subset of strategies $\overline{\Pi} \subset \Pi$, define

$$\mathcal{L}_{\overline{\Pi}} \triangleq \bigcup_{\pi \in \overline{\Pi}} \mathcal{P}(\pi).$$

Definition 3 (Completeness for the expected average cost [4, Def. 4.2]). A class of strategies $\overline{\Pi} \subset \Pi$ is called *complete for the expected average cost optimality criterion* (for a given initial state distribution β) if

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\overline{\Pi}} \quad \text{and} \quad |\mathcal{P}(\pi)| = 1 \quad \forall \pi \in \overline{\Pi}.$$

Definition 4 (Dominating strategies [4, Def. 2.2]). A class of strategies $\overline{\Pi} \subset \Pi$ is said to be *dominating for the CMDP* if for any feasible strategy $\pi \in \Pi$, there exists a feasible strategy $\overline{\pi} \in \overline{\Pi}$ such that

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \mathbb{E}_{\overline{\pi}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^T c(S_t, A_t) \right] \leq \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \mathbb{E}_{\pi} \left[\sum_{t=1}^T c(S_t, A_t) \right].$$

Lemma 14 ([4, Thm. 4.2]). Let $\overline{\Pi} \subset \Pi$ be the set of stationary strategies in a CMDP. Then $\mathcal{L}_{\overline{\Pi}}$ is a closed convex polytope.

Proof. The full proof is available in [4, Thm. 4.2]. We omit it here for brevity. The key step of the proof is to show that $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\overline{\Pi}} = \mathcal{Q}$, where \mathcal{Q} is a closed convex polytope defined as

$$\mathcal{Q} = \left\{ \rho(s, a) \mid s \in \mathcal{S}, a \in \mathcal{A}, \sum_{\hat{s} \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \rho(y, da) (\mathbb{1}_{x=y} - \mathbb{P}[s|\hat{s}, a]) = 0 \ \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \right. \\ \left. \sum_{\hat{s} \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \rho(\hat{s}, a) = 1 \right\}.$$

□

Theorem 7. *Under the unichain assumption (T4.1), any stationary strategy profile π in Game 2 induces a Markov chain with a unique stationary distribution that is independent of the initial state distribution. As $t \rightarrow \infty$, the state occupancy measures converge to this distribution.*

Proof. (T4.1) implies that all states $s \in \mathcal{S}$ are positive recurrent in the induced Markov chain. Hence, the chain is irreducible and recurrent [79, Thm. 5.3.3]. Consequently, it follows from the fundamental theorem of Markov chains that the chain has a unique stationary distribution [79, Thm. 5.5.12]. Furthermore, (T4.1) implies that each state $s \in \mathcal{S}$ is aperiodic in the induced Markov chain. This aperiodicity means that we can invoke the convergence theorem of Markov chains, which states that the state occupancy measures converge to the stationary distribution as $t \rightarrow \infty$ [79, Thm. 5.6.6]. □

The following corollary is an immediate consequence of Theorem 7.

Corollary 4. *Under assumption (T4.1), any strategy profile π in Game 2 induces a unique occupancy measure $\rho \in \Delta(\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{S}} \times \{0, 1\})$.*

Lemma 15. *Given a feasible strategy pair π in Game 2, the expected average cost (7) can be expressed as*

$$\mathbb{E}_{\pi}[J] = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{S}}} \sum_{a^{(C)} \in \{0, 1\}} \rho_{\pi}(s, a^{(C)}) a^{(C)},$$

where $\rho_{\pi} \in \Delta(\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{S}} \times \{0, 1\})$ is the occupation measure induced by π .

Proof. We know from Cor. 4 that ρ_{π} exists. As a consequence, it follows from (7) that

$$\mathbb{E}_{\pi}[J] = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbb{P}[A_t^{(C)} = 1] = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{S}}} \sum_{a^{(C)} \in \{0, 1\}} \rho_{\pi}(s, a^{(C)}) a^{(C)}. \quad (22)$$

□

Lemma 15 implies the following corollary.

Corollary 5. *Given an attacker strategy $\pi^{(A)}$, and an occupation measure ρ_π such that*

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_S} \sum_{a^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \rho_\pi(s, a^{(C)}) a^{(C)} \leq \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_S} \sum_{a^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \rho_{(\pi^{(C)}, \pi^{(A)})}(s, a^{(C)}) a^{(C)} \quad \forall \pi^{(C)},$$

then the following strategy is a best response for the controller:

$$\hat{\pi}^{(C)}(a^{(C)} | s) = \frac{\rho_\pi(s, a^{(C)})}{\sum_{\hat{a}^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \rho_\pi(s, \hat{a}^{(C)})} \quad \forall s \text{ where } \sum_{\hat{a}^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \rho_\pi(s, \hat{a}^{(C)}) > 0.$$

Lemma 16.

- (A) *If the attacker follows a stationary strategy, then the class of stationary controller strategies $\pi^{(C)}$ in Game 2 is complete and dominant (Defs. 3–4).*
- (B) *If the controller follows a stationary strategy, then the class of stationary attacker strategies $\pi^{(A)}$ in Game 2 is complete and dominant (Defs. 3–4).*

Proof. We only give the proof for (A) since the proof of (B) is analogous. Let Π denote the set of controller strategies, let $\pi^{(A)}$ be a stationary attacker strategy, and let $f_S(s' | s, a^{(C)}, \pi^{(A)})$ be the transition function induced by $\pi^{(A)}$. We know from [4, Thm. 2.1] that the class of Markov strategies is dominating, which means that we can restrict Π to the class of Markov strategies.

To show that the class of stationary Markov strategies is complete, it suffices to show that for any $\pi^{(C)} \in \Pi$, there exists a stationary strategy $\hat{\pi}^{(C)} \in \Pi$ such that $\rho_{(\pi^{(C)}, \pi^{(A)})} = \rho_{(\hat{\pi}^{(C)}, \pi^{(A)})}$. Towards this end, we define $\hat{\pi}^{(C)}$ as

$$\hat{\pi}^{(C)}(a^{(C)} | s) \triangleq \begin{cases} \frac{\rho_\pi(s, a^{(C)})}{\sum_{\hat{a}^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \rho_\pi(s, \hat{a}^{(C)})} & \text{if } \sum_{\hat{a}^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \rho_\pi(s, \hat{a}^{(C)}) \geq 0 \\ \text{arbitrary} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

It follows from Cor. 4 that $\hat{\pi} = (\hat{\pi}^{(C)}, \hat{\pi}^{(A)})$ induces a unique occupation measure $\rho_{\hat{\pi}}$ that satisfies

$$\rho_{\hat{\pi}}(s, a^{(C)}) = \rho_\pi(s) \hat{\pi}^{(C)}(a^{(C)}, s).$$

Now note that

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_\pi(s') &= \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_S} \sum_{a^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \rho_\pi(s, a^{(C)}) f_S(s' | s, a^{(C)}, \pi^{(A)}) \\ &= \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_S} \rho_\pi(s) \sum_{a^{(A)} \in \{0,1\}} \hat{\pi}^{(C)}(a^{(C)} | s) f_S(s' | s, a^{(C)}, \pi^{(A)}) \\ &= \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_S} \rho_\pi(s) \mathbb{P}[S' = s' | S = s, \hat{\pi}]. \end{aligned}$$

The above equality implies that $\rho_\pi(\cdot)$ is a stationary distribution of the Markov chain induced by $\hat{\pi}$. We know that this distribution is unique (Thm. 7). Hence, $\rho_\pi = \rho_{\hat{\pi}}$. \square

Lemma 17. *A linear program with a bounded and non-empty feasible region has an optimal solution.*

Proof. Follows from the fundamental theorem of linear programming, see [78, Cor. 2.3]. \square

R.1 Proof of Theorem 4.A

A consequence of Lemma 16 is that if a pair of best responses exists, then there also exists a pair of stationary best responses. Further, Cor. 5 implies that if we obtain the best response occupation measure, we can obtain the best response strategies. These properties imply that we can invoke Lemma 15, which asserts that given a stationary attacker strategy $\pi^{(A)}$, a best response controller strategy can be obtained from the solution to the following linear program:

$$\underset{\boldsymbol{\rho}}{\text{minimize}} \quad \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_S} \sum_{a^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} a^{(C)} \boldsymbol{\rho}(s, a^{(C)}) \quad (23)$$

subject to

$$\boldsymbol{\rho}(s, a^{(C)}) \geq 0 \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}_S, a^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_S} \sum_{a^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \boldsymbol{\rho}(s, a^{(C)}) = 1$$

$$\sum_{a^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \boldsymbol{\rho}(s, a^{(C)}) = \sum_{s' \in \mathcal{S}_S} \sum_{a^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \boldsymbol{\rho}(s', a^{(C)}) f_S(s' | s, a^{(C)}, \pi^{(A)}) \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}_S$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}_S} \sum_{a^{(C)} \in \{0,1\}} \boldsymbol{\rho}(s, a^{(C)}) \mathbb{1}_{s \geq f+1} \geq \epsilon_A,$$

where $f_S(s' | s, a^{(C)}, \pi^{(A)})$ is the transition function induced by $\pi^{(A)}$.

Similarly, an analogous linear program gives a best response for the attacker. Now note that it follows from Assumption (T4.2), Lemma 14, and Lemma 17 that there exist optimal solutions to these linear programs. Hence, stationary best responses exist. \square

R.2 Proof of Theorem 4.B

A comprehensive proof with a step-by-step verification of all necessary conditions and intermediary lemmas can be found in [80, Thm. 2.1]. We provide a short version of the proof here. Let $\mathcal{B}_C(\pi^{(A)})$ and $\mathcal{B}_A(\pi^{(C)})$ be the best response correspondences for the controller and the attacker, respectively. It follows from Theorem 4.A that these correspondences correspond to the optimal solutions to the linear program in (23). Now let $\mathcal{B}(\boldsymbol{\pi}) \triangleq \mathcal{B}_C(\pi^{(A)}) \times \mathcal{B}_A(\pi^{(C)})$. By definition, a fixed point of \mathcal{B} is a constrained Markov equilibrium of Game 2. It follows from standard properties of linear programs that \mathcal{B} has a compact and convex range and is upper hemi-continuous [80, Prop. 3.1]. Hence, by the closed graph theorem, $\mathcal{B}(\boldsymbol{\pi})$ has a closed graph for each $\boldsymbol{\pi}$. It then follows from Kakutani's

fixed point theorem that a constrained Markov equilibrium of Game 2 exists [81]. Since this equilibrium is independent of the initial state and since all states are recurrent (T4.1), the equilibrium is also an MPE (Def. 2). \square

Appendix S The Service Availability Constraint in Game 2

The allowed service downtime per year for different values of ϵ_A is shown in Table 9.

ϵ_A	<i>Allowed service downtime per year</i>
0.7	108 days
0.8	72 days
0.9	36 days
0.95	18 days
0.99	3 days
0.999	8 hours
0.9999	52 minutes
0.99999	5 minutes
0.999999	31 seconds
1	0 seconds

Table 9: Allowed service downtime for different values of ϵ_A .

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